

Pop-Machina

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Data Management Plan

Deliverable 1.3

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14/11/2019

<http://www.pop-machina.eu>

Abstract

The current report constitutes the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the Pop Machina project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. Under this framework, the initial version of the Data Management Plan describes the data management processes to be followed during the lifecycle of the project, along with the methodology employed in order to ensure the FAIR provisions for data management. It builds on the GDPR guidelines and provides information about the data to be collected/generated throughout the Pop-Machina activities, as well as details about the procedures to be followed in order to make this data openly accessible. It defines the data management responsibilities, sets the premises on data security and provides a template for collecting and monitoring changes with regard to data management. This version of the Data Management Plan sets a basic framework of necessary actions, as perceived at this early stage of the project. As the project matures, the DMP will be updated in order to depict any changes in the data that needs to be collected or any modifications in the data processing tools, methods, etc.

This report constitutes Deliverable D1.3 for Work Package 1 of the Pop-Machina project.

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1. Introduction

The current document represents the first version of the Pop-Machina Data Management Plan (DMP), which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (Grant Agreement No 821479).

Pop-Machina aims to demonstrate the power and potential of the maker movement and collaborative production for the EU circular economy. We draw from a number of cut-edge technologies (factory-of-the-future, blockchain) and disciplines (urban planning, architecture) to provide the support necessary to overcome scaling issues; a typical drawback of collaborative production; to find the areas more in need of our intervention and to reconfigure unused spaces. The project puts forth an elaborate community engagement program to network, incentivize and stimulate through maker faires and events existing and new maker communities in all our municipalities. It builds upon the current informal curriculum for maker skills development by nurturing the social side and we put educators and makers together to exchange ideas on the training modalities. A particular focus on the skill development of women and vulnerable groups will aim to empower these (underrepresented) segments to partake actively in collaborative production.

The project will demonstrate in every pilot area business oriented collaborative production of feasible and sustainable concepts from secondary raw material or other sustainable inputs, based on the needs and preferences of the local stakeholders. A thorough impact assessment framework with increased scope (e.g. social) will be codesigned with stakeholders after short basic assessment trainings and will be used in the assessment of our pilot work. Based on the findings, it will kick-start a series of policy events to discuss openly – without pushing our results – the tax and legal barriers that hamper collaborative production.

For Pop-Machina to be successful, **all partners of Pop-Machina's consortium will adhere to sound common data management principles** in order to ensure that the meaningful data collected, processed and/or generated throughout the duration of the project are well-managed, archived and preserved, in line with the [Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020](#).

Along these lines, this **initial version of the DMP** aims to achieve the following **objectives**:

- describe the data management lifecycle for the data to be collected and/or generated in the framework of Pop-Machina, serving as the key element of good data management;
- outline the methodology employed to safeguard the sound management of the data collected, and/or generated as well as to make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR);
- provide information on the data that will be collected and/or generated and the way in which it will be handled during and after the end of the project along with the standards applied to this end;
- describe details on how the data will be made openly accessible and searchable to interested stakeholders as well as its curation and preservation;
- present information on the resources to be allocated to make data FAIR clearly identifying the responsibilities pertaining to data management and considering data security across the entire lifetime of data.

The DMP is structured in 7 distinct chapters, as follows:

- **Chapter 1** presents the Pop-Machina context and outlines the objectives and structure of the DMP;
- **Chapter 2** outlines the purpose and objectives of the Pop-Machina activities which ultimately lead to the data collection and generation processes. In addition, it presents data types and formats, origin, expected volume and relevant stakeholders that might utilise the data;
- **Chapter 3** describes the processes followed in order to ensure FAIR data management during the entire lifecycle of the Pop-Machina;
- **Chapter 4** provides an estimation of the resources required to ensure FAIR data management and defines the respective responsibilities;
- **Chapter 5** outlines the data security strategy followed by Pop-Machina, along with the implemented secure storage procedures;
- **Chapter 6** addresses ethical aspects regarding the collected/generated data;
- **Chapter 7** summarises the conclusions of this document and presents the next steps foreseen for updating the DMP.

The DMP is a dynamic document. It is expected to evolve during the lifespan of the project and will be **further elaborated and updated throughout the duration of the project.** Additional updates may also be realised, in order to include new data, better detail and/or reflect any changes in the methodology or other aspects relevant to their management, changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors. KU Leuven is responsible for the elaboration of the DMP; the support of all partners is necessary for keeping the document updated.

2. Data summary

Pop-Machina is set to collect, generate and re-use non-sensitive data that is **not included into any special categories**¹ of personal data as those are described within the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).² We expect that this data will comprise of quantitative, qualitative or a mixture of both and will be analysed using diverse methodological approaches to provide insights that will successfully meet Pop-Machina's activities. This chapter of the DMP defines the purpose of the data collected/generated under the framework of Pop-Machina along with a detailed description of data types and formats, data origins and expected size. It concludes with an overview of data utility and potential stakeholders that might find the data useful for re-use.

Regarding personal data in particular, it should be noted that the Pop-Machina consortium aims at ensuring that the GDPR guidelines are considered throughout and all personal data collected or generated within the project activities are going to (i) be **transparent** in terms of how they will be used (principle of transparency) and (ii) be **restricted to the minimum required** in order to fulfil the objective under which it was collected (principle of economy).

2.1 Types and formats of collected/generated data

Pop-Machina is set to utilise collected/generated data of diverse structure and format. As a result, the data definition process can be based on the source and the physical format of the data³. We note two main aspects: (i) the process under which the underlying data is created/captured, which may include the use of electronic texts documents, spreadsheets, online questionnaires and notes, among others, and (ii) the storage format of quantitative and qualitative data, which may include easily accessible formats, such as post scripts (e.g. pdf, xps, etc.), machine-readable formats (xml, html, xhtml, rdf, json, etc.), spreadsheets, (e.g. xlsx, csv, etc.), text documents (e.g. docx, rtf, txt, etc.), compressed file formats (e.g. rar, zip, gzip, etc.) or any other format required by the objectives and methodology of the activity within the frame of which the data is produced.

Partners should opt for file formats that do not require usage of commercial software or specific operating system when possible e.g. **open formats** (such as csv, pdf, zip, etc.) and/or **machine-readable format** (such as xml, json, rdf, html, etc.).

The type and formats of the data collected/generated in the context of Pop-Machina can be divided into **these categories**:

- data collected/generated by **direct input methods** (i.e. feedback from interviews and online surveys, desk research, feedback from users and stakeholders, validation processes, etc.) (e.g. WP2, WP3, WP6, WP7);

¹ Special categories of personal data according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation) include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

² Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>.

³ Jakobsson, U., Braukmann, R., Lundgren M., Expert Tour Guide on Data Management. Retrieved from <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/1.-Plan>.

- data collected/generated during the process of mapping pilot areas, collecting legal information about pilot profiles and so on (e.g. WP2);
- empirical data collected during behavioural experimentation (WP3);
- data collected/generated through the **Pop-Machina platform and its services** (i.e. input inserted by platform's users, data generated from the platform's services, data retrieved from other sources - e.g. WP4);
- data collected/generated through the pilot activities (WP5);
- data collected/generated from dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities (WP8).

2.1.1 Data collected/generated by direct input methods

- **Data collected about existing innovation and business development support services in the circular maker ecosystem.** This data will be collected by the project partners, and will originate in their own organisations or organisations that they are in contact with, or freely available online sources. The data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in a standard spreadsheet (.xlsx). At present, no activities are foreseen that would include their re-usage. This data will be used to design the innovation and business support services for the circular maker ecosystems of Pop-Machina.
- **Data collected about existing acceleration programmes (objectives, length, structure, curricula, learning material).** This data will be collected by the project partners, and will originate in their own organisations or organisations that they are in contact with, or freely available online sources. The data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in a standard spreadsheet (.xlsx). There is a possibility to reuse them at a later stage, to support access to funding and leading acceleration programmes. This data will be used to design and deploy a well-tailored acceleration program to foster entrepreneurship among the circular maker communities of Pop-Machina.
- **Data collected from questionnaires to collect feedback on the services' performance and outcomes.** This data originates from the Service Satisfaction Survey Questionnaire and the Service Impact Survey questionnaire that will be completed by the makers that received support through the Pop-Machina acceleration programme. The data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in standard text files (.docx, .pdf) or standard spreadsheets (.xlsx). They will be reused to improve the innovation and business development support services of Pop-Machina.
- **Data collected through the process that will take place for the selection of most promising makers in order to receive business modelling and planning services.** This data originates from the assessment/voting process that will take place to identify the best candidates-maker teams to receive the business modelling and planning services of Pop-Machina, based on criteria such as approach, impact, and team and budget. The data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in standard text files (.docx, .pdf) or standard spreadsheets (.xlsx). At present, no activities are foreseen that would include their re-usage. This data will be used to identify the maker teams that will receive the business modelling and planning services of Pop-Machina.
- **Data collected about existing funding opportunities.** This data will be collected by the project partners, and will originate in their own organisations or organisations that they are in contact with, or freely available online. The data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in a standard spreadsheet (.xlsx). At present, no activities are foreseen that would include their re-usage. This data will be used to identify possible funding opportunities for the Pop-Machina maker teams in the framework of EU funding, national funding, municipality funding, and private funding sources.

2.1.2 Data collected/generated through the pilot activities

During the design and preparations for the pilot deployment plan data will be collected to find out ideas and opinions of local stakeholders in order to co-develop a pilot deployment plan together.

During the pilot operation data will be collected:

- to understand the overall performance of the pilot projects;
- to understand performance of methods and tools developed in the previous WPs.

These data will originate from pilot project participants, makerspaces and project partners.

Types and formats of data that the project generate/collect include:

- interview transcripts (.docx);
- questionnaire responses (.xlsx);
- workshop results (filled-in exercise sheets) (.xlsx);
- workshop photos (.jpeg);
- statistics on sustainable production in each makerspace, including material use, machinery use, environmental impact (.xlsx).

Data generated in parallel and after the pilots. The data generated in WP6 relate to stimulation of the innovation and business opportunities that will arise from the collaborative production pilot cases in the circular makers ecosystems of the participating cities, and further their support by the Pop-Machina consortium to finding a route-to-market and accessing finance. The purpose of the data collection is to inform the design and delivery of integrated innovation and business support services to our maker communities, followed by a customised acceleration program; to inform the design and delivery of tailored business plans to the most promising circular productions; and to identify and promote suitable contacts and networks between the maker communities and potential funders and investors.

2.1.3 Data collected/generated from dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities

The data generated in WP8 relate to the dissemination and communication of Pop-Machina project. The purpose of the data collection is for the monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication results of the project, with a view to measuring the impact of the relevant activities, fine tuning Pop-Machina's strategy accordingly, as well as fulfilling its reporting requirements towards the commission:

- **data collected from the dissemination events** (e.g. stakeholder engagement events, etc.) This data will be updated every time a partner organises or attends an event. Finally, the data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in a standard spreadsheet (.xlsx);
- **data collected from the Social media statistics** (including Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube). This data will be collected/generated through periodic monitoring of the Pop-Machina's social media statistics with a view to measuring and assessing the performance and results of the project's social media activity in terms of dissemination and communication. Data will be both qualitative as well as quantitative in nature addressing the metrics reached on each channel (e.g. followers, tweets impressions on twitter, friends, likes on Facebook, etc.). The data are expected to be stored in a spreadsheet file (.xlsx) while at the same time the analysis of the results will be stored in a standard word document (.docx);
- **data collected from the Newsletter subscriptions** (e.g. contact details of subscribers) In order to enhance the dissemination activities of the project, newsletter subscriptions are foreseen in the

project's website. A subscription form will facilitate the collection of this data in which any interested stakeholder can voluntarily provide his/her contact details in a dedicated sign-up form, so as to receive the most up-to-date news and outcomes of the project. Along these lines, the data will be comprised of a list of stakeholders along with their basic contact information: (i) email address, (ii) first and last name, (iii) country, (iv) type of organisation, (v) region and (vi) gender. A copy of this contact list will be stored to MailChimp's server which is used for e-mail campaigns and newsletter distribution. All personal information included in this contact list will be used and protected according to MailChimp's Privacy Policy;

- **data collected from the Network of Interest** (e.g. contact details of stakeholders) This data refers to contact information data from relevant stakeholders who will constitute the Pop-Machina's Network of Interest. All members of the network will receive a semi-annual newsletter depicting the project progress and will be encouraged to participate in technical/scientific discussions via the project website and other communication means. This data will be utilised by project partners in order to invite members to the learning workshop which will be organised in M36 of the project.

2.1.4 Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data

New data will be collected/generated throughout the project both by consortium partners, as well as external stakeholders participating in the relevant actions or using the Pop-Machina platform (e.g. makers, citizens, fablab owners, SMEs). Any potential risk or data management issue with regard to external stakeholders should be identified and addressed as much as possible in a proactive manner.

Pre-existing data are also foreseen to be collected/generated and utilised during the project's implementation, referring to open secondary data sources from official statistical services (i.e. EUROSTAT). A detailed inventory of already known and available data sources will be envisaged, including among others open platforms and other exploitable web-based sources. In all cases, the source of the data will be referenced in the relevant document with a specific link.

2.2 Expected size of data

The DMP will gather and present the different activities implemented within the course of the project in which data is collected/generated, the types and formats of the data, as well as the expected size of the data. This table is expected to be embedded in the second version of this deliverable.

2.3 Data utility

The stakeholder groups that may find meaningful utility for the data to be collected/generated by the project (both within and outside of the Pop-Machina's consortium), along with the benefits that could arise for them by utilising this data, are concisely presented in the Table that follows.

Table 1 Data Utility

Stakeholder group	Data utility
Makers and fablab owners/professionals	The project aims at helping alleviate the barriers that new or existing makers face in accessing collaborative production activities. The project will expectedly collect and create novel data sources relevant for this stakeholder group, providing them in an open access format for them to be further exploited in meaningful ways (e.g. through the Pop Machina website/platform). Key assets to be utilized by the makers

Stakeholder group	Data utility
	group are circular designs, training modules, and also all relevant material hosted on the Pop-Machina platform (e.g. collaborative production features, tokenization scheme).
Policy makers, urban planners, local authorities	The project will provide considerable primary sources of data, including their processed output, that are essential in analyzing and supporting policy makers and decision makers in the EU, at a national and local level. These data can be used for studying a wide range of relevant fields, like planning, design, sourcing of fabrication labs and makerspaces, and also for expanding our understanding on makers' needs, drivers and barriers for potential or existing opportunities, and also data on actual roll out of circular collaborative production.
Academics/Researchers	Pop-Machina is set to collecting/generating data that is of considerable interest to academia and researchers. In this respect, the produced Pop-Machina datasets pave the way for addressing some of the most under-researched questions in the empirical literature, concerning the empirical examination of circular economy in the crossroads with collaborative production, ICT and cryptography technology, industry 4.0., urban planning and so on. Given that most of these subareas are characterized by a fastly growing interest we expect the usefulness of our novel dataset to be significant for researchers.
Project partners	Data collected/generated under the frame of Pop-Machina is set to provide real-life directions and insights to project partners which will ultimately utilize them towards reaching the project's objectives. This data will provide valuable information for the design of the Pop-Machina methodologies and assessment criteria, the co-design, development and fine-tuning of the project's platform, as well as the targeted promotion of the project outcomes. Moreover, this data can empower the design and validation of sustainable business models which will enhance the impact and market competitiveness of Pop-Machina. Finally, capitalization of interesting ideas and concepts created during the project's lifespan will foster post-project exploitation and long-term sustainability of Pop-Machina's offerings. Project partner data utility will be detailed in the exploitation deliverable.

3. FAIR data

The [Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020](#) of the Commission highlight the importance of making the data produced by projects funded under Horizon 2020 **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable as well as Reusable (FAIR)**,⁴ with a view to ensuring its sound management. This means using standards and metadata to make data discoverable, specifying data sharing procedures and which data will be open, allowing data exchange via open repositories as well as facilitating the reusability of the data. The following sections of the DMP lay out the methodology followed in the framework of Pop-Machina with respect to making data findable, accessible and interoperable, as well as ensuring their preservation and open access, with a view to increasing its re-use.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Data discoverability and identification mechanisms

Pop-Machina will aim to enhance the discoverability of the collected/generated data during its activities. To this end, the project follows a metadata-driven approach to increase the searchability of the data, while also facilitating its understanding and re-use. Metadata is defined as “data about data” or “information about information”.⁵ This entails structured textual information that describes something about the creation, content, or context of a digital resource – be it a single file, part of a single file, or a collection of many files. Metadata is the tool that helps people to discover, manage, describe, preserve and build relationships with and between digital resources;⁶ three distinct types of metadata exist.⁷

Data produced/used under the activities of Pop-Machina will be discoverable using metadata suitable to its content and format. The project will employ **metadata standards** to produce rich and consistent metadata to support the long-term discovery, use, and integrity of its data.

The consortium will explore and may opt to have **data produced by Pop-Machina and considered open for re-use be deposited to Zenodo**⁸ an open data repository. In this way, we could attempt to further increase **data discoverability**. Zenodo can enable open access to the project’s open data free of charge. It builds and operates a simple service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions, among others, to share and showcase research results (including data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. It supports all file formats, promotes peer-reviewed openly accessible research, allows the creation of own collections and it is available free of charge both for Pop-Machina to upload and share data as well as for other stakeholders to explore, download and re-use this data.

4 Wilkinson, M. D. et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* 3:160018, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

5 Huxley, L., & Jacobs, N. (2004). *Online information services in the Social Sciences*. Oxford: Chandos.

6 Foulonneau, M., & Riley, J. (2008). *Metadata for digital resources: Implementation, systems design and interoperability*. Oxford: Chandos.

7 Caplan, P. (2003). *Metadata fundamentals for all librarians*. Chicago: American Library Association.

8 www.zenodo.org.

Moreover, by employing this data repository, the data produced during the implementation of the project is locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism. Pop-Machina will be able to assign globally resolvable Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) on any data uploaded to Zenodo. An identifier is a unique identification code that is applied to a dataset so that it can be unambiguously referenced.⁹ PIDs are simply maintainable identifiers that allow for permanent reference to a digital object. In other words, PIDs are a way of giving digital resources, such as documents, images and data records, a unique and persistent reference number.

Zenodo registers **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)** for all submitted data through [DataCite](#), which is the leading global non-profit organisation that provides PIDs (and specifically DOIs) for research data, and preserves these submissions using the safe and trusted foundation of CERN's data centre, alongside the biggest scientific dataset in the world, the LHC's 100PB Big Data store.¹⁰ DOIs remain valuable since they are future proofed against Uniform Resource Locator (URL) or even protocol changes, through resolvers (such as [DOI](#)). At the same time, **datasets not uploaded to Zenodo will be deposited in a searchable resource (i.e. cloud storage of the platform) and utilise well-tailored identification mechanisms** as well, in the form of standard naming conventions that will safeguard their consistency and make them **easily locatable** for project partners within the framework of the project.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

3.2.1 Openly available and closed data

Pop-Machina is part of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) that aims to “*make the data collected/generated by selected projects openly available with as few restrictions as possible, while at the same time protecting sensitive data from inappropriate access*”. The project adopts the good practice encouraged by the ORDP, namely that of making data **as open as possible and as closed as necessary**. This calls for project partners to disseminate the project's data that have the potential to offer long-term value to external stakeholders and do not harm the confidentiality and privacy of the stakeholders that contributed in the collection/generation of this data, with a view to maximising the beneficial impact of Pop-Machina.

Where applicable, the Amnesia,¹¹ OpenAIRE's data anonymization tool will be employed to relevant datasets ensuring that anonymised and aggregated data will be made open while data subjects cannot be identified in any reports, publications and/or datasets resulting from the project. The project partner serving as the data controller in each case will undertake all the necessary anonymisation procedures to anonymise the data in such a way that the data subject is no longer identifiable.

⁹ Tonkin, E. Persistent identifiers: considering the options (2008), Ariadne Issue 56.

¹⁰ Retrieved from: <https://www.software.ac.uk/tags/zenodo>.

¹¹ <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>.

Table 2 Good Practices for Data Anonymisation

Type of data	Good practices
Quantitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remove or aggregate variables or reduce the precision or detailed textual meaning of a variable. - Aggregate or reduce the precision of a variable such as age or place of residence. Generally, report the lowest level of geo-referencing that will not potentially breach respondent confidentiality. - Generalise the meaning of a detailed text variable by replacing potentially disclosive free-text responses with more general text. - Restrict the upper or lower ranges of a continuous variable to hide outliers if the values for certain individuals are unusual or atypical within the wider group researched.
Qualitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use pseudonyms or generic descriptors to edit identifying information, rather than blanking-out that information. - Plan anonymisation at the time of transcription or initial write-up, (longitudinal studies may be an exception if relationships between waves of interviews need special attention for harmonised editing). - Use pseudonyms or replacements that are consistent within the research team and throughout the project. For example, using the same pseudonyms in publications and follow-up research. - Use ‘search and replace’ techniques carefully so that unintended changes are not made, and misspelled words are not missed. - Identify replacements in text clearly, for example with [brackets] or using XML tags such as <seg>word to be anonymised</seg>. - Create an anonymisation log (also known as a de-anonymisation key) of all replacements, aggregations or removals made and store such a log securely and separately from the anonymised data files.

Source Tour guide on data management of the CESSDA¹²

OpenAIRE’s Amnesia ensures that data identifiers are removed, generalised, aggregated or distorted. Moreover, anonymisation is different than pseudonymisation, which falls under a distinct category in the GDPR - anonymisation theoretically destroys any way of identifying the data subject, while pseudonymisation allows for the data subject to be re-identified with additional information. Along these lines, the table above provides a list of good practices for the anonymisation of quantitative and qualitative data derived from the tour guide on data management of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA).

The following table presents the data collected/generated during the project that will be made openly available. In case certain data cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), a justification for that choice is provided. It is important to note that **all personal data collected/generated will be considered as closed data prior to their anonymisation and aggregation to safeguard the confidentiality of the data subjects.**

¹² Retrieved from: <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/5.-Protect/Anonymisation.>

Table 3 Data Availability

No	Data	Availability	Notes
1	Literature and state of the art reviews	Open	No expected issues
2	Interviews with relevant stakeholders	Open	Any personal information data will be aggregated/anonymised before being made openly available.
3	Surveys	Open	Any personal information data will be aggregated/anonymised before being made openly available.
4	Ideas and feedback collected during the Pop-Machina stakeholder activities (e.g. workshops)	Open	Moderators will make sure to anonymize all the material produced (e.g. minutes, reports) and will ask for informed consent otherwise.
5	Multisource data used in urban analytics models and graphs	Most probably closed	Applies the most restrictive license of a dataset integrated into the various urban graphs.
6	Direct data input by users to the Pop-Machina platform	Closed	Since they can contain personally identifiable data or sensitive information.
7	Data generated from the platform's services	Closed	Since they can contain personally identifiable data or sensitive information. Aggregated anonymized statistical data can be provided as open.
8	Data retrieved from behavioural experiments	Open	Fully anonymized data sets can be made open.
9	Feedback on Pop-Machina's pilots	Open	Feedbacks gathered through pilots will be handled and reported in an aggregated form, without any reference to personal or sensible data, and after anonymisation of the data (as following mentioned).
10	Social media statistics	Open	Any personal information data will be aggregated/anonymised before being made openly available.
13	Data collected from dissemination events	Open	Any personal data will be treated as expected by the GDPR. Other data should be made open unless special conditions document a different action.
14	Newsletter subscriptions	Closed	This data will remain closed as it contains personal information and is useful only for internal reporting purposes.

3.2.2 Data accessibility and availability

Public access to the open data will be pursued through relevant available solutions. In this early stage the solution that is put forth is Zenodo – the consortium might consider other options as the project matures¹³. Zenodo which will automatically link to OpenAIRE. The data will be fully accessible thanks to the included metadata and the search facility available on Zenodo. At the same time, closed data are intended to be stored and shared amongst authorised members of the consortium through cloud storage and file sharing providers which constitute structures that maintain and manage data and make this data accessible over the internet. The following table presents where we expect data to be made accessible in the context of Pop-Machina.

Table 4 Data accessibility

No	Data	Accessibility
1	Literature and state of the art reviews	Zenodo
2	Interviews with relevant stakeholders	Zenodo
3	Surveys	Zenodo
4	Ideas and feedback collected during the Pop-Machina stakeholder activities (e.g. workshops)	Zenodo
5	Multisource data used in urban analytics models and graphs	Pop-Machina platform under restrictive license
6	Direct data input by users to the Pop-Machina platform	Authorized personnel only, through the Pop-Machina platform
7	Data generated from the platform's services	Authorized users only, through the Pop-Machina platform
8	Data retrieved from behavioural experiments	Pop-Machina platform and/or Zenodo
9	Feedback on Pop-Machina's pilots	Zenodo
10	Social media statistics	- Closed data, available only within the consortium. - Aggregated data on Zenodo.
11	Data collected from dissemination events	Closed data, available only within the consortium
12	Newsletter subscriptions	Zenodo

¹³ The rest of the report will consider the Zenodo option, but this should not pre-empt the consortium from a different well-documented alternative.

No	Data	Accessibility
13	Literature and state of the art reviews	Zenodo
14	Interviews with relevant stakeholders	Closed data, available only within the consortium

3.2.3 Methods, software tools and documentation to access the data

Pop-Machina emphasises the accessibility of the data collected/generated during the project. No specialised method, software tool and/or documentation is expected to be needed at the moment, in order to access the data. Stakeholders will have the ability to access the data by simply using their web browser (e.g. Mozilla, Google Chrome, Internet Explorer, Safari, etc.) through their computers (either desktop or laptop), smart phones and/or tablets. In the case of Zenodo, users need to access the platform through its webpage (following the link <https://zenodo.org/>) and utilise the search engine of the repository to search for interesting data. Closed data will be accessed by authorised project partners through the usage of a cloud storage (through the platform) or online file sharing systems. Again, no specialised method, software tool and/or documentation is needed to this end.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability refers to the ability of systems and services that create, exchange and use data to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context, and meaning of that data.¹⁴ Pop-Machina will adopt – where applicable - in its data management methodology the use of metadata vocabularies, standards, and methods that will increase the interoperability of the data collected/generated through its activities. The interoperability of the data that will not be publicly shared will be facilitated using the Dublin Core Metadata standard. This standard is a small “metadata element set” which accounts for issues that must be resolved in order to ensure that data meet traditional standards for quality and consistency while remaining broadly interoperable with other data sources in the linked data environment. The interoperability of openly available data will be facilitated through Zenodo since its metadata will be stored internally in JSON format.

3.4 Increase data re-use

3.4.1 Licence schemes to permit the widest use possible

The application of a licence to Pop-Machina’s open data is a simple way to ensure that any interested third-party can re-use it. Licences are the instrument which permit a third-party to copy, distribute, display and/or modify the project’s data only for the purposes that are set by the licence. Licences typically grant permissions on condition that certain terms are met. While the precise details vary, three conditions are commonly found in licences which are the attribution, non-derivative, and non-commerciality. Pop-Machina intends to publish its openly available data under the Creative Commons licencing scheme to foster their re-use and build an equitable and accessible environment for them. Zenodo provides Pop-Machina the opportunity to publish its open data under five Creative Commons licences as follows:

¹⁴ L. Steele & T. Orrell (2017). The frontiers of data interoperability for sustainable development. Publish What You Fund and Development Initiatives.

- **Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0** (CC BY-SA 4.0) according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, must be distributed under the same license as the original. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made;
- **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International** (CC BY 4.0) according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made;
- **Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivatives 4.0 International** (CC BY-ND 4.0) under which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made;
- **Creative Commons Attribution-Non Commercial 4.0 International** (CC BY-NC 4.0) based on which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get permission by project partners first. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made;
- **Creative Commons Attribution-Non Commercial-No Derivatives 4.0 International** (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0) according to which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get permission by project partners first. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

Different licensing schemes may be selected to better fit the need of Pop-Machina’s open data ensuring not only their long-term preservation and re-use but also the interests of the consortium along with the rights of individuals for whom the data is about. In such a case, this subsection of the DMP will be updated accordingly.

3.4.2 Data quality assurance processes

Quality Assurance (QA) and **Quality Control** (QC) activities are an integral part of Pop-Machina’s data management methodology and are implemented prior to the publication of any data to Zenodo, safeguarding the transparency, consistency, comparability, completeness, and accuracy of the data.

QA is a planned system of review procedures conducted outside the framework of developing a dataset, by personnel not directly involved in the dataset development process¹⁵. In the context of Pop-Machina, it takes the form of **peer-reviews of methods and/or data summaries** to assess the quality of the dataset and identify any need for improvement, ensures that the dataset correctly incorporates the scientific knowledge and data generated.

QC is defined as a system of checks to assess and maintain the quality of the dataset being compiled¹⁶. The relevant procedures of Pop-Machina are designed to provide routine technical checks as they measure and control data consistency, integrity, correctness, and completeness as well as identify and address errors and omissions. In this context, QC checks cover everything from data acquisition and handling, application of approved procedures and methods, and documentation. Some of the general quality checks undertaken in the framework of the project include checking (i) for transcription errors in data input; (ii) that scale measures are within the range of acceptable values; and (iii) whether proper naming conversions are used.

Data quality will be aligned and work as an addendum to the quality plan (in D1.1 Pop Machina Project Management Handbook).

¹⁵ 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER 6 Quality Assurance/Quality Control and Verification.

¹⁶ 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER 6 Quality Assurance/Quality Control and Verification.

4. Allocation of resources

4.1 Data management responsibilities

Effective, proper and secure handling of the Pop-Machina data collected/generated requires the establishment of specific data management roles within the data management methodology and procedures of the project. These responsibilities are outlined in this section of the DMP as follows.

Project Coordinator (PC): The PC (KU Leuven), is responsible for overall data management in the framework of Pop-Machina, including the elaboration of the DMP and its updates (when necessary along with support of all partners). At the same time, the PC is responsible for the elaboration of proper templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to be appropriately adjusted and utilised by project partners during the relevant activities of the project. Finally, the PC coordinates with Work Package and Task Leaders to determine whether and how the data collected/generated by the project are shared and become available for re-use, contributes to its quality assurance and uploads the project's openly available data to Zenodo.

Work Package Leaders (WPL): The WPL are responsible for coordinating the implementation of the data processing activities performed under the WPs they are leading. They align with the PC and the respective Work Task Leader on whether and how the data gathered/produced under the tasks that fall within the WP they are leading will be shared and/or re-used. This includes the definition of access procedures as well as potential embargo periods along with any necessary software and/or other tools which may be required for data sharing and re-use. Finally, the WPL are the main responsible for assuring the quality of the data stemming from the activities of the WP they are leading, including assessing their quality and indicating any need for improvement to the respective Work Task Leaders.

Task Leaders (TL): The TL act as **data controllers**¹⁷ of the data collected/generated in the frame of the tasks that fall under their leadership, determining the purposes and means of processing this data as well as safeguarding its appropriate and timely processing. Moreover, they are responsible for properly adjusting the templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to the needs and specificities of the activities carried out in the task they are leading. Finally, they undertake any necessary actions to prepare the data collected/generated through the tasks they are leading for sharing either within the consortium or openly (including the use of proper naming conventions, application of suitable anonymisation techniques, the creation of appropriate metadata and documentation, etc.). The decision of online or printed consent forms will be taken in collaboration with the WPL.

Data processors: Data processors are project partners that are tasked to collect, digitise, anonymise, store, destroy and/or otherwise process data for the specific purpose of the activity in which it has been collected/generated within the framework of the project. They are responsible for appropriately collecting the necessary consent for processing data as well as for ensuring that the informed consent form and information sheet used to this end is properly adjusted to the needs of the activity they are participating and any particularities applicable to their organisation. Moreover, they are also responsible for managing the consents they have retrieved with a view to demonstrating their compliance with the relevant applicable EU and national regulation. Finally, they perform quality checks to assess and maintain the quality of the dataset(s) held within their records.

¹⁷ According to the GDPR data controller means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data.

Data repositories: Data repositories are tasked with the storage and long-term preservation of the project's data. In this respect, Zenodo maintains and preserves the openly available data of Pop-Machina, enabling its sharing and re-use. Zenodo assigns metadata and DOIs to the data, while also taking all the necessary measures to securely back-up the data and be able to restore it, safeguarding its long-term preservation.

5. Data security

Pop-Machina will **securely handle any collected/generated data** throughout its entire lifecycle as it is essential to safeguard this data against accidental loss and/or unauthorised manipulation. Particularly, in case of personal data collection/generation it is crucial that this **data can only be accessible by those authorised to do so**. The project's back-up and data recovery strategy aims at ensuring that no data loss will occur during the course and after the completion of Pop-Machina, either from human error or hardware failure, as well as inhibit any unauthorised access.

All project partners are responsible for processing¹⁸ data within their private servers and will ensure that this **data is protected**, and any **necessary data security controls have been implemented**, to minimize the risk of information leak and destruction. This case refers to the data that will be closed and therefore will not be shared and/or re-used within the framework of the project. In this case, in order to avoid data losses, the data will be **backed up regularly** to safeguard their preservation, while also enabling their recovery at any time.

Access to closed data will only be permitted to authorised project partners. In case there is a **personal data breach, project partners will notify, without undue delay** and, where feasible, **not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it, their competent national supervisory authorities** (e.g. data protection authorities) **as well as the data subject(s) that may be affected by the breach**. Moreover, they will document any personal data breaches, including information such as the facts relevant to the breach, its effects and the remedial action(s) taken.

Identification and authentication access controls play an important role in the context of the project, as they help partners to protect the data collected/generated during Pop-Machina and especially personal data. To this end, each project partner is responsible for and committed to ensuring the application of appropriate access controls to the data they are processing within their private servers of their organisation. At the same time, **technical access controls will be foreseen to be built into the Pop-Machina Web Portal and the Pop-Machina platform**, setting out clear roles with access rights to the data stored there so that only authorised personnel have access. Each project partner will be provided with unique accounts containing one or more roles assigned to them and at the same time enforcing role-based security when its staff processes the project's data. These accounts are expected to be username/password protected, maximising access control. Moreover, in order to safeguard the privacy of the users of the project's Web Portal and Pop-Machina platform, dedicated **privacy policies** will define the way in which these online spaces collect, process and use personal data, the security procedures followed, the users' rights as well as the cookies policy employed.

¹⁸ Processing, according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation), means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

6. Ethical aspects and other procedures

This Section concerns with the ethical aspect of the Pop-Machina DMP and the ethical compliance of the underlying data foreseen to be collected/generated under the project's activities. The project will process data that are not included in any special category of personal data¹⁹ (i.e. non-sensitive data). The collection/generation of this data from individuals participating in the project's activities is based upon a **process of informed consent**. Any personal data collected/generated in the framework of Pop-Machina is processed according to the principles laid out by the **Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016** on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data which has entered into force in May 2018 aiming to protect individuals' rights and freedoms in relation to the processing of their personal data, while also facilitating the free flow of such data within the European Union. Along these lines, **data is collected/generated only for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes** relative to the project's objectives. Moreover, all project partners tasked with processing data during Pop-Machina fully abide with their respective applicable national as well as EU regulations.

It is important to highlight that **each project partner is responsible for ensuring that the templates for the Information Sheet as well as the Informed Consent Form are appropriately adjusted** according to (i) the needs of the activity for which they are being used by them as well as to (ii) the relevant regulations applicable to their respective countries and/or organisation. Moreover, **all partners should keep records to demonstrate that an individual has consented to the processing of his/her personal data** and use consent management mechanisms that make it easy for individuals to withdraw their consent.

The templates for the Information Sheet and the Informed Consent Form, used in the implementation of the project's activities, are compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation and annexed to this DMP (see Annex).

¹⁹ Special categories of personal data according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation) include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

7. Conclusions and way forward

This initial version of the Pop-Machina DMP aims at describing the process for the management of the data collected/generated during the project's activities across their entire lifecycle, while also making them compatible with the FAIR scheme. It describes the underlying processes of the Pop-Machina data management, collection and generation, in accordance with the GDPR guidelines, and sheds light on (i) the data foreseen to be collected/generated under the project activities, (ii) the specific objectives under which each dataset will be collected/generated, (iii) the data management roles and responsibilities and (iv) the data security and ethical aspects of the data.

In the framework of Pop-Machina, the DMP is a dynamic document that will be updated throughout the course of the project. It is expected to be further developed and updated another three times throughout the duration of Pop-Machina (i.e. as D1.4 by M12, D1.5 M24 and D1.6 by M48). If necessary, additional ad hoc updates may be realised in order to include new data, better detail and/or reflect modifications in the methodologies applied or other aspects relevant to data management (such as costs for making data FAIR, size of data, etc.), changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors.

8. DMP components template

8.1 DMP components for WP (number) - (WP Title) - Guidance

DMP component	Issues to be addressed
Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? b) What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect? c) Will you re-use any existing data and how? d) What is the origin of the data? e) What is the expected size of the data? f) To whom might the data be useful (“data utility”)?
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable and identifiable? (Guidance: Discoverability and identifiability of the data means: The data are provided with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)) b) What naming conventions do you follow? (Guidance: e.g. Data_<WPno>_<serial number of dataset>_<dataset title> Example: Data_WP1_1_Data Management Plan) c) Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? d) Do you provide clear version numbers? e) What metadata will be created? (Guidance: Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what type of metadata will be created and how.)
Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? (Guidance: If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.) b) How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)? c) What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? (Guidance: e.g., if you are using proprietary programs or file formats to generate and store your research data.)

	<p>d) Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?</p> <p>e) Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?</p> <p>f) Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? (Guidance: Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.)</p> <p>g) Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?</p> <p>h) If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?</p> <p>i) Is there a need for a data access committee?</p> <p>j) Are there well-described conditions for access (i.e. a machine-readable license)?</p> <p>k) How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>a) Are the data produced in the project interoperable? (Guidance: Interoperability of data means: allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins).)</p> <p>b) What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?</p> <p>c) Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your dataset, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?</p> <p>d) In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?</p>
<p>Increase data re-use</p>	<p>a) How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?</p> <p>b) When will the data be made available for re-use? (Guidance: If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.)</p> <p>c) Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? (Guidance: If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.)</p> <p>d) How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?</p> <p>e) Are data quality assurance processes described?</p>

Allocation of resources	<p>a) What are the costs for making data FAIR for your project? (Guidance: Please calculate the expected costs (software, human resources) for the research data management.)</p> <p>b) How will these be covered?</p> <p>c) Who will be responsible for data management in your project?</p> <p>d) What are the costs and potential value of long-term preservation?</p>
Data security	<p>a) Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long-term preservation and curation?</p> <p>b) What provisions are in place for data security? (Guidance: Data security includes data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.)</p>
Ethical aspects	<p>a) Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?</p> <p>b) Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?</p>
Other issues	<p>a) Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?</p>

8.2 DMP components for WP (number) - (WP Title)

DMP component	Issues to be addressed
Data summary	
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
Making data openly accessible	
Making data interoperable	
Increase data re-use	
Allocation of resources	
Data security	
Ethical aspects	
Other issues	

About Pop-Machina

Pop-Machina aims to demonstrate the power and potential of the maker movement and collaborative production for the EU circular economy. We draw from a number of cut-edge technologies (factory-of-the-future, blockchain) and disciplines (urban planning, architecture) to provide the support necessary to overcome scaling issues; a typical drawback of collaborative production; to find the areas more in need of our intervention and to reconfigure unused spaces. We put forth an elaborate community engagement program to network, incentivize and stimulate through maker faires and events existing and new maker communities in all our municipalities. We build upon the current informal curriculum for maker skills development by nurturing the social side and we put educators and makers together to exchange ideas on the training modalities. A particular focus on the skill development of women and vulnerable groups will aim to empower these (underrepresented) segments to partake actively in collaborative production. In every pilot area we will demonstrate business oriented collaborative production of feasible and sustainable concepts from secondary raw material or other sustainable inputs, based on the needs and preferences of the local stakeholders. A thorough impact assessment framework with increased scope (e.g. social) will be codesigned with stakeholders after short basic assessment trainings and will be used in the assessment of our pilot work. Based on the findings we will kick-start a series of policy events to discuss openly – without pushing our results – the tax and legal barriers that hamper collaborative production.

Coordinator

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Partners

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CREVIS (BE)
Municipality of Thessaloniki (GR)
Municipality of Piraeus (GR)
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL (GR)
University of Macedonia (GR)
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